

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4004241>

Pathogenesis of IL-6 and potential therapeutic of IFN- γ in COVID-19

Ahmed Hasan Mohammed

University of Thi-Qar, College of Science, Nasiriyah, Dhi Qar, Iraq

E-mail: ahmedhasan5@sci.utq.edu.iq

Received: 16 July 2020; **Revised submission:** 16 August 2020; **Accepted:** 26 August 2020<http://www.journals.tmkarpinski.com/index.php/ejbr>Copyright: © The Author(s) 2020. Licensee Joanna Bródka, Poland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

ABSTRACT: The elevated inflammatory cytokines suggest that a cytokine storm, also known as cytokine release syndrome (CRS), may play a major role in the pathology of pandemic Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) leading to cause Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and multiple organ dysfunction then death. However, there was a controversial efficacy of corticosteroids in the treatment of COVID-19 induced cytokine release syndrome (CRS). Novel therapies to treat COVID-19-induced CRS become urgent needed. One of the most common cytokine that showed to be critical in the COVID-19 is the IL-6 and this article discuss the pathogenesis of this cytokine in severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS). Also, this article proposes to utilize interleukin-6 (IL-6) blockade and potential therapeutic effect of IFN- γ to manage COVID-19-induced CRS and discuss several factors that should be taken into consideration for its clinical application.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2; COVID-19; IL-6; IFN- γ .

1. INTRODUCTION

The recently developing coronavirus ailment 2019 (COVID-19), first announced in Wuhan, China, has cleared across 202 nations with dazzling mortality. The World Health Organization (WHO) has announced this dangerous flare-up a pandemic, with gigantic implications affecting each life. By March 27, 2020, the quantity of passings had move to 23,495 among 512,701 affirmed cases in WHO reports [1]. Serious intense respiratory disorder coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), a novel beta-coronavirus, has been recognized as the pathogen for COVID-19, separately [2]. SARS-CoV-2 focuses on the lung and likely different organs also, prompting multiple organs harm by official to the angiotensin-changing over catalyst 2 (ACE2) receptor [2], a cell surface protein exceptionally communicated in the lung, heart and kidney [3].

Clinical information from Wuhan, China, indicated that roughly 17.7–32.0% of patients require emergency unit level consideration, with around 9.5–12.0 days from manifestation beginning to multiple organs dysfunctions, in particular, intense respiratory misery condition (ARDS) (67%), intense kidney injury (29%), intense heart injury (23%), and liver brokenness (29%) [4-6]. The mortality of fundamentally sick patients is as high as 49.0–61.5% [4, 5]. Proof proposes that CRS may assume a significant job in extreme COVID-19. Incendiary cytokines and chemokines, including interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), instigated protein 10 (IP10) and monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1) were fundamentally raised in COVID-19 patients, and some were more normally observed in extreme patients than in non severe patients.

In COVID-19 patients with raised provocative cytokines, after death pathology has uncovered tissue rot and interstitial macrophage and monocyte invasions in the lung, heart and gastrointestinal mucosa [7, 8]. In addition, extreme lymphopenia with hyperactivated proinflammatory T cells [8] and diminished administrative T cells [9] is generally observed in fundamentally sick patients, recommending dysregulated safe reactions.

Right now, there are no particular antibodies or medicines for COVID-19. Be that as it may, there are numerous continuous clinical preliminaries assessing likely medicines. WHO will keep on giving refreshed data when clinical discoveries become accessible [7]. The infection seems to spread effectively among individuals, and researchers will keep on finding increasingly about how it spreads. The information indicated that it is spread from individual to individual through close contact (inside 6 feet, or 2 meters). The infection is spread by respiratory beads discharged when the contaminated individual hacks, wheezes or talks. This splash can be breathed in, or entered the individual's mouth or nose. It can likewise be transmitted if an individual contacts a surface on which the infection is contaminated and afterward contacts his mouth, nose, or eyes [8].

Signs and side effects may seem 2 to 14 days after introduction. The period following introduction and before the beginning of side effects is known as the "hatching period". Basic signs and indications can incorporate fever, coughing, tired Shortness of breath or trouble breathing, muscle torment, chills, sore throat, losing a feeling of taste or smell, headache and chest torment [9].

The COVID-19 flare-up has majorly affected clinical microbiology research centers in the previous a while., gathering the correct respiratory tract example at the ideal time from the privilege anatomic site is basic for a brief and exact atomic analysis of COVID-19. Suitable measures are required to guard research facility staff while creating solid test outcomes. In the logical stage, constant opposite translation PCR (RT-PCR) examines remain the sub-atomic trial of decision for the etiologic determination of SARS-CoV-2 disease while counter acting agent based methods are being presented as supplemental devices. In the postanalytical stage, testing results ought to be cautiously deciphered utilizing both sub-atomic and serological discoveries [10]. At last, irregular access, incorporated gadgets accessible at the purpose of care with adaptable limits will encourage the quick and exact analysis and observing of SARS-CoV-2 contaminations and extraordinarily aid the control of this episode [10].

2. ROLE OF IL-6 IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF COVID-19

Outside the body, among them we accept that the IL-6 bar is a promising technique for CRS instigated by COVID. We have seen that raised IL-6 levels have been reliably revealed in numerous COVID-19 investigations It might fill in as a biomarker for anticipating sickness seriousness. An enormous review study found that IL-6 levels were related with mortality in patients with COVID-19 [6]. Precisely, IL-6 is important to create T assistant cells T17 (Th17) in dendritic cell interaction [10] between T cells Excessive IL-6 may clarify unnecessarily initiated Th17 cells saw in COVID-19 patients, as announced by Xu et al. [8] Although clinical information are not accessible for the IL-6 bar in a CRS related with viral disease, creature investigations of SARS-CoV have shown that hindrance of the atomic factor Kappa-B (NF- κ B), which is a significant translation factor for IL-6, or injury Animals with SARS-CoV come up short on the infection envelope protein (E), which is a solid impetus for NF- κ B signals, has expanded creature endurance, with lower IL-6 levels [11] Interestingly, we saw that the E proteins of SARS-CoV-2 (reference grouping QHD43418.1) and SARS-CoV (reference succession NP_828854.1) share 95% of the evenness. Since E

protein is destructive explicit and intervenes the host resistant reaction to the Coronavirus [12, 13], it is sensible to guess that both infections react to a comparative invulnerable reaction. Along these lines, IL-6 focusing on might be compelling in CRS actuated by COVID. Among the exorbitant cytokines delivered by energizer macrophages, IL-6 is one of the significant cytokines. Raised degrees of IL-6 were seen in SARS patients and related with serious disease [14], IL-6 initiates its last Janus kinase (JAK) signal by appending the layer (CIS signals) or the dissolvable structure (signal exchange) of the IL-6 receptor (IL-6R) and collaborating with the film related gp130 [15]. Extreme IL-6 signs lead to incalculable natural impacts that add to organ harm, for example, the development of guileless T cells into responsive T cells, incitement of endothelial vascular development factor (VEGF) articulation in epithelial cells, expanding vessel porousness [10], and diminishing myocardium contractility [16].

Given the adequacy of tocilizumab in CRS and the significant job of IL-6 in COVID-19, we recommend reuse of tocilizumab to treat serious instances of COVID-19. Concerning clinical use, we propose that the accompanying components be thought about and we trust that future clinical preliminaries will have the option to address them. Symptomatic measures There is at present no agreement in diagnosing CRS in COVID-19. Early analysis of CRS in COVID-19 patients and brief commencement of immunotherapy might be helpful, as recommended by the HLH [17] preliminary. Quick assessment of COVID-19 patients with H-score, which is an analytic level of HLH, may help separate patients with CRS malady seriousness characterization system [18]. Involvement in immunotherapy-activated CRS proposes that tocilizumab is just suggested for extreme cases, while evaluating the advantage of hazard is desirable over indicative administration for gentle cases. This methodology is advocated by worry that forceful mitigating treatment may nullify the impact of restorative organic substances, for example, CAR T cells. This rule isn't partaken in viral diseases, for example, COVID-19, as it might forestall ideal mediation in mellow patients or Moderates progress.

Tocilizumab is an acculturated monoclonal counter acting agent against IL-6R. It ties both the solvent IL-6R and the film-related layer to square IL-6-intervened flags and transmits signals [19]. Tocilizumab is affirmed by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration for the treatment of CRS incited CRS prompted by CRS T cells [20]. As referenced before, CRS is the most serious unfavorable impact brought about via CAR T cell treatment, with a rate of 50-100% [19]. Official of CAR T cell receptors to their antigen prompts incitement of neighboring cells to discharge monstrous measures of IFN and tumor rot factor TN (TNF- α), which builds the enactment of inborn safe cells, including macrophages and endothelial cells, to emit IL-6 other provocative middle people [21]. IL-6 is a focal merchant for poisonousness in IL-6 CRS actuated CAR [20-22]. Clinically, extreme instances of CAR-T instigated CRS present with fever, hypoxia, intense renal disappointment, hypotension, and cardiovascular arrhythmia that regularly warrants ICU confirmation [20]. Tocilizumab indicated promising adequacy in extreme CRS After one portion One or two dosages of tocilizumab, 69% of patients reacted inside 14 days, fever and hypotension were settled inside hours, and vasopressors could be immediately weaned in a few days [23, 24]. The impact of tocilizumab on CRS has likewise been accounted for in numerous different conditions, for example, sepsis, unite versus-have ailment (GvHD), macrophage actuation disorder MAS [25-27]; Furthermore, Tocilizumab is ok for the two kids and grown-up patients as no unfriendly responses have been accounted for in the review investigation of patients with CARS-instigated CRS [19]. The most widely recognized antagonistic impact is disease in patients with rheumatoid joint inflammation, where constant treatment is kept up for a more extended timeframe (3.11-3.47/100 man a long time with 8 mg/kg of Tocilizumab at regular intervals) [28]. Furthermore, a potential relationship has been

accounted for among tocilizumab and tranquilize related bone putrefaction in the jaws in patients with osteoporosis. A past companion study proposed that IL-6 levels were fundamentally raised in COVID-19 patients however varied essentially between both ICU patients and non-ICU patients.

This perception brings up the issue of whether the IL-6 bar is successful just in patients with high serum IL-6 levels. Assuming this is the case, the IL-6 estimation might be an essential piece of the evaluating framework. In addition, the IL-6 level alone may not be adequate to mirror its utilitarian impacts on the estuary Screening that recognizes IL-6 from practical IL-6 may give an improved way to deal with controlling treatment choices. C-receptive protein (CRP), an intense fiery stage in the protein that is incorporated by IL-6 subordinate hepatocyte amalgamation, a solid indication of IL-6 bioactivity and used to anticipate CRS severity. The adequacy of IL-6 barricade was checked for patients with T-cell-instigated CRS. The CRP level was not decided in the infection prompted CRS. Most investigations have recommended that raised CRP levels were related with extreme COVID-19 [30-32], with somewhere in the range of barely any special cases [29]. Notwithstanding, future examinations are required on imperative finishes paperwork with the end goal of delineation of dangers and observing of remedial impact. There is additionally a large group of accessible organic specialists that target distinctive basic particles in the fiery system, for example, IL-1, IL-18, TNF, IFN or Janus kinase transducer/sign and transducer trigger (JAK)/STAT signals. These variables may likewise be useful, and provided that this is true, a standard estimation of cell aggravation is justified.

3. POTENTIAL THERAPEUTIC EFFECT OF IFN IN COVID-19

New helpful intercessions will probably require a long lead time for the improvement of affirmed drugs. Hence, considering the critical need and criticalness to recognize the treatment and control of COVID-19, a repurposing of IFNs and other affirmed drugs is an expected alternative in tranquilize improvement for the control of coronavirus contamination. The potential medication alternatives for SARS-CoV-2 disease incorporate the utilization of compound inhibitors, nucleosides, have focused on specialists, gaining strength plasma and IFNs.

Interferon are a gathering of proteins normally created by invulnerable framework cells because of disease with different pathogens. Interferon was first portrayed in 1957 by Asiacs and Landmann, researchers from the London National Institute for Medical Research. Interferon was named after it was seen as ready to "meddle" in viral translation.

The fundamental elements of (interferon): from one perspective, they forestall infections from increasing (in light of the fact that they enact the creation of particles that forestall viral proliferation) and then again, they actuate crafted by other insusceptible cells whose capacity is to wipe out "ailing cells" (for example, cells contaminated with the infection), bacterial cells or neoplastic cells. Human interferon is delivered in three gatherings: alpha, beta and gamma [33].

Interferon is utilized as splashes and is given to the patient by vanishing through the respirator framework, in light of the fact that, as indicated by specialists from the Center for Genetic and Biotechnology Engineering CIGB, Havana it speaks to a fast technique that arrives at the lungs and can work in the beginning periods of injury. In the current examination, the host reacted to a coronavirus contamination inside the retina by enlisting monocytes and T cells into the influenced retina and creating IFN- γ . At the point when retinal infection occurred in mice deficient in IFN- γ , the virus was not examined, and the infection resulted in death. These investigations likewise indicated that IFN- γ was critical in controlling retinal infection disease. A few proof lines demonstrate that IFN- γ was working at different levels. Initially, IFN-state caused an anti-viral

state in uninfected cells which brought about a lower recurrence of the JHM (coronavirus in rats) information not this demonstrated can expand the movement of T cells and cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs). Second, it can be encouraged by expanding the guideline of MHC Class I on the influenced cells and enlistment of transducer CTL [34]. Third, IFN- γ of enactment of macrophages may deliver extra cytokines, which can expand immune reaction.

At last, IFN- γ improve can support safe response by inciting MHC class I molecules [35]. IFN- γ is a significant safe protein that applies its effect on an assortment of cells and cell capacities. In instances of infection contaminations, including coronavirus diseases, this cytokine Th1 has been appeared to control infection repeat central sensory system infected with coronavirus.

4. CONCLUSION

COVID-19 is a complex disease and need extraordinary measures for controlling spreading of the virus and providing special cure procedures. Reduce the inflammatory condition that caused by SARS-CoV-2 inside the body is one of the methods to control the pandemic of the disease and using of IL-6 blockers and IFN- γ must be provided by the Governments for rapid cure of patients and decrease the fatality rate of the disease.

Conflict of Interest: The author has no conflict of interest to declare.

Acknowledgment: I would like to express my special thanks of gratitude to my students for helping me in the assembly of this article.

REFERENCES

1. WHO. 2020. Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation Report – 67.
2. Zhou P, Yang XL, Wang XG, Hu B, Zhang L, Zhang W. A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature*. 2020. 579: 270-273.
3. Turner AJ, Hiscox JA, Hooper NM. ACE2: from vasopeptidase to SARS virus receptor. *Trends Pharmacol Sci*. 2004. 25: 291-294.
4. Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Emergency Response Epidemiology Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Emergency Response Epidemiology Team. The epidemiological characteristics of an outbreak of 2019 novel coronavirus diseases (COVID-19) in China. *Chin J Tubercul Respir Dis*. 2020; 41: 145-151.
5. Yang X, Yu Y, Xu J, Shu H, Xia J, Liu H. Clinical course and outcomes of critically ill patients with SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a single-centered, retrospective, observational study. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2020; 2600(20)30079-5.
6. Zhou F, Yu T, Du R, Fan G, Liu Y, Liu Z. Clinical course and risk factors for mortality of adult inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study. *Lancet*. 2020; 395: 1054-1062.
7. Yao XH, Li TY, He ZC, Ping YF, Liu HW, Yu SC. A pathological report of three COVID-19 cases by minimally invasive autopsies. *Chin J Pathol*. 2020; 49: E009.
8. Xu Z, Shi L, Wang Y, Zhang J, Huang L, Zhang C. Pathological findings of COVID-19 associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2020; 8: 420-422.
9. Qin C, Zhou L, Hu Z, Zhang S, Yang S, Tao Y. Dysregulation of immune response in patients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020; 71(15): 762-768.

10. Tanaka T, Narazaki M, Kishimoto T. Immunotherapeutic implications of IL-6 blockade for cytokine storm. *Immunotherapy*. 2016; 8: 959-970.
11. DeDiego ML, Nieto-Torres JL, Regla-Nava JA, Jimenez-Guardeno JM, Fernandez-Delgado R, Fett C. Inhibition of NF-kappaB-mediated inflammation in severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-infected mice increases survival. *J Virol*. 2014; 88: 913-924.
12. Nieto-Torres JL, DeDiego ML, Verdia-Baguena C, Jimenez-Guardeno JM, Regla-Nava JA, Fernandez-Delgado R. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus envelope protein ion channel activity promotes virus fitness and pathogenesis. *PLoS Pathog*. 2014; 10: e1004077.
13. Schoeman D, Fielding BC. Coronavirus envelope protein: current knowledge. *Virology*. 2019; 16: 69.
14. Zhang Y, Li J, Zhan Y, Wu L, Yu X, Zhang W. Analysis of serum cytokines in patients with severe acute respiratory syndrome. *Infect Immun*. 2004; 72: 4410-4415.
15. Johnson DE, O'Keefe RA, Grandis JR. Targeting the IL-6/JAK/STAT3 signalling axis in cancer. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*. 2018; 15: 234-248.
16. Pathan N, Hemingway CA, Alizadeh AA, Stephens AC, Boldrick JC, Oragui EE. Role of interleukin 6 in myocardial dysfunction of meningococcal septic shock. *Lancet*. 2004; 363: 203-209.
17. Henter JI, Chow CB, Leung CW, Lau YL. Cytotoxic therapy for severe avian influenza A (H5N1) infection. *Lancet*. 2006; 367: 870-873.
18. Mehta P, McAuley DF, Brown M, Sanchez E, Tattersall RS, Manson JJ. COVID-19: consider cytokine storm syndromes and immunosuppression. *Lancet*. 2020; 395: 1033-1034.
19. Le RQ, Li L, Yuan W, Shord SS, Nie L, Habtemariam BA. FDA approval summary: tocilizumab for treatment of chimeric antigen receptor T cell-induced severe or life-threatening cytokine release syndrome. *Oncol*. 2018; 23: 943-947.
20. Neelapu SS, Tummala S, Kebriaei P, Wierda W, Gutierrez C, Locke FL. Chimeric antigen receptor T-cell therapy - assessment and management of toxicities. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*. 2018; 15: 47-62.
21. Shimabukuro-Vornhagen A, Godel P, Subklewe M, Stemmler HJ, Schlosser HA, Schlaak M. Cytokine release syndrome. *J Immunother Cancer*. 2018; 6: 56.
22. Norelli M, Camisa B, Barbiera G, Falcone L, Purevdorj A, Genua M. Monocyte-derived IL-1 and IL-6 are differentially required for cytokine-release syndrome and neurotoxicity due to CAR T cells. *Nat Med*. 2018; 24: 739-748.
23. Lee DW, Gardner R, Porter DL, Louis CU, Ahmed N, Jensen M. Current concepts in the diagnosis and management of cytokine release syndrome. *Blood*. 2014; 124: 188-195.
24. Wang D, Hu B, Hu C, Zhu F, Liu X, Zhang J. Clinical characteristics of 138 hospitalized patients with 2019 novel coronavirus-infected pneumonia in wuhan, China. *J Am Med Assoc*. 2020; 323: 1061-1069.
25. De Benedetti F, Brunner HI, Ruperto N, Kenwright A, Wright S, Calvo I. Randomized trial of tocilizumab in systemic juvenile idiopathic arthritis. *N Engl J Med*. 2012; 367: 2385-2395.
26. Kennedy GA, Varelias A, Vuckovic S, Le Texier L, Gartlan KH, Zhang P. Addition of interleukin-6 inhibition with tocilizumab to standard graft-versus-host disease prophylaxis after allogeneic stem-cell transplantation: a phase 1/2 trial. *Lancet Oncol*. 2014; 15: 1451-1459.
27. Sheng F, Han M, Huang Z, Zhang L. Interleukin 6 receptor inhibitor tocilizumab suppresses cytokine expression, inflammasome activation and phagocytosis in a cell model of sepsis. *Pharmazie*. 2016; 71: 636-639.

28. Burmester GR, Rubbert-Roth A, Cantagrel A, Hall S, Leszczynski P, Feldman D. Efficacy and safety of subcutaneous tocilizumab versus intravenous tocilizumab in combination with traditional DMARDs in patients with RA at week 97 (SUMMACTA). *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2016; 75: 68-74.
29. Chen L, Liu HG, Liu W, Liu J, Liu K, Shang J. Analysis of clinical features of 29 patients with 2019 novel coronavirus pneumonia. *Chin J Tubercul Respir Dis.* 2020; 43: E005.
30. Gao Y, Li T, Han M, Li X, Wu D, Xu Y. Diagnostic utility of clinical laboratory data determinations for patients with the severe COVID-19. *J Med Virol.* 2020; 92(7): 791-796.
31. Liu Y, Yang Y, Zhang C, Huang F, Wang F, Yuan J. Clinical and biochemical indexes from 2019-nCoV infected patients linked to viral loads and lung injury. *Sci China Life Sci.* 2020; 63(3): 364-374.
32. Wang Z, Yang B, Li Q, Wen L, Zhang R. Clinical features of 69 cases with coronavirus disease 2019 in wuhan, China. *Clin. Infect. Dis.* 2020; 71(15): 769-777.
33. Vilcek J, Sen GC. Interferons and other cytokines Fields, BN Knipe, DM Howley, PM eds. *Virology* 1, 375-399 Lippincott-Raven Philadelphia. 1996.
34. Viores S, Wang Y, Viores MA. Blood-retinal barrier breakdown in experimental coronavirus retinopathy: association with viral antigen, inflammation, and VEGF in sensitive and resistant strains. *J Neuroimmunol.* 2001; 119: 175-182.
35. Pearce BD, Hobbs MV, McGraw TS, Buchmeier MJ. Cytokine induction during T-cell-mediated clearance of mouse hepatitis virus from neurons in vivo. *J Virol.* 1994; 68: 5483-5495.